

The Structure of the Elusive Simplest Dipeptide Gly-Gly

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Abstract: Among the hundreds of peptide compounds whose conformations have been determined by different spectroscopic techniques the structure of the simplest dipeptide glycyl-glycine (Gly-Gly) is conspicuously absent. Herein, for the first time solid samples of Gly-Gly have been vaporized by laser ablation and three different structures have been revealed in a supersonic expansion by Fourier transform microwave spectroscopy. The intramolecular hydrogen bonding interactions that stabilize the observed forms have been established on the bases of the ^{14}N nuclear quadrupole hyperfine structure. We have illustrated how conformer interconversion distorts the equilibrium conformational distribution giving rise to missing conformers in the conformational panorama.

The structural features and folding mechanism of polypeptides and proteins may first be tackled through the investigation on the conformational properties of isolated short peptides, with the latter as a prelude to the former. Since in condensed phases their conformational tendencies are strongly biased by solvent interactions or crystal packing forces, is the gas phase which has provided the isolation conditions necessary to determine their intrinsic conformational preferences of these flexible systems. To date, natural di- and tripeptides derived from aromatic amino acids such as Trp-Ser,^[1] Pro-Trp,^[2] Gly-Tpr,^[3,4] Phe-Gly-Gly,^[5] Tyr-Gly-Gly^[6] or Trp-Gly-Gly^[4,7] have been investigated in the gas phase by double-resonance (UV-UV, IR-UV) laser spectroscopy, taking advantage of the presence of a chromophore group. Unfortunately, their non-aromatic counterparts, containing for example amino acids as relevant as glycine, alanine or proline, are elusive to such experimental studies due to the absence of chromophores. It is remarkable among all the non-aromatic dipeptides the case of the simplest dipeptide glycylglycine (Gly-Gly) (Scheme 1), formed by condensation of two units of amino acid glycine, since to date no experimental investigations of these relevant molecule have been carried out to elucidate its conformational landscape. Gly-Gly, a solid with high melting point ($\sim 263^\circ\text{C}$) and low vapor pressure, is well-known for its thermal instability, preventing easy measurements of its gas-phase spectra. Its conformational behavior remain unknown and its investigation has been, until now, restricted solely to the theoretical field.^[8]

Scheme 1. Schematic representation of Gly-Gly molecule with indication of its 6 internal torsional degrees of freedom which can give rise to conformational isomers. N_t and N_c make reference to the NH_2 terminal and NH central nitrogen atoms respectively.

Nowadays, advances in laser ablation techniques have made possible transferring bare biomolecules into the gas phase to probe their most stable conformers in the isolated environment of a supersonic expansion by laser ablation molecular beam Fourier transform microwave spectroscopy (LA-MB-FTMW).^[9] Although the excellent results achieved in natural amino acids^[10,11] and capped dipeptides^[12-15] have boosted the investigation of Gly-Gly, the numerous attempts to acquire its rotational spectrum failed due to the photofragmentation problems inherent to the laser ablation process.^[16] In the present investigation, latest improvements of our laser ablation system^[17,18] addressed to minimize photofragmentation effects, have finally conducted to the first rotational study of the simplest Gly-Gly dipeptide. Experimental details are included in the Supporting Information.

Figure 1. (Upper) The stick diagram of the observed spectra of the Gly-Gly in the region of 3-6 GHz showing rotational transitions of the X, Y and Z rotamers. (Lower) Nuclear quadrupole hyperfine structure for the $212 \leftarrow 101$ rotational transition of rotamer X. The energy levels involved in each transition are labeled with the quantum numbers J , K_{-1} , K_{+1} , l , F and each hyperfine component is labeled with the corresponding values of l' , $F' \leftarrow l''$, F'' quantum numbers.

Gly-Gly rotational spectrum, Figure 1, is dominated by lines exhibiting well resolved hyperfine structure with many components spreading several MHz, which were accounted for in terms of ^{14}N nuclear quadrupole coupling interaction. Gly-Gly possesses two ^{14}N nuclei (N_c and N_t) (see Scheme 1) with a nuclear quadrupole moment $I = 1$, which interacts with the electric field gradient created at each nitrogen atom position by the molecular charge distribution.^[19] This nuclear quadrupole coupling interaction couples the nuclear spin and the rotation angular momentum which makes each rotational line split in a complex pattern. The spectroscopic parameters extracted from this interaction can be used as a structural diagnostic reporting on the hydrogen bonding architecture of the conformations.^[16,20] Several sets of μ_a -type and μ_b -type R-branch rotational transitions were ascribed to three different rotamers of Gly-Gly, labeled as X,

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Y and Z. Rotamer X only showed *b*-type rotational spectrum while the rotamers Y and Z exhibited both *a* and *b*-type spectra. For all of them the complex ^{14}N nuclear quadrupole hyperfine structure was fully resolved, as illustrated in Figure 1. Hence, a total of 51, 29 and 34 nuclear hyperfine components belonging to X, Y and Z rotamers respectively (see Tables S2–S4 in the Supporting Information) were measured and analyzed^[21] using a Watson's A-reduced rigid rotor Hamiltonian^[22] supplemented with a term to account for the nuclear quadrupole coupling interaction.^[19,23] The determined rotational (*A, B, C*) and quadrupole coupling constants ($\chi_{aa}, \chi_{bb}, \chi_{cc}$) from the fits are collected in Table 1.

Table 1. Experimental spectroscopic parameters derived for the three observed rotamers of Gly-Gly.

	Rotamer X	Rotamer Y	Rotamer Z
<i>A</i> ^[a]	3124.81219 (66)	5056.1357 (11)	3380.9980 (11)
<i>B</i>	846.30680 (17)	668.787909 (17)	912.71335 (35)
<i>C</i>	675.17061 (12)	597.87466 (15)	798.10977 (29)
<i>P_c</i>	5.18436 (14)	5.16257 (13)	34.98346 (25)
$^{14}\text{N}_t$			
χ_{aa}	-3.6379 (24)	0.106 (17)	-1.6209 (25)
χ_{bb}	2.6732 (36)	-1.474 (19)	0.6953 (82)
χ_{cc}	0.9647 (36)	1.368 (19)	0.9257 (82)
$^{14}\text{N}_c$			
χ_{aa}	2.4907 (25)	2.301 (20)	1.6781 (52)
χ_{bb}	1.2924 (32)	1.959 (20)	1.1034 (84)
χ_{cc}	-3.7831 (32)	-4.259 (20)	-2.7814 (84)
<i>N</i>	51	29	34
σ	2.3	2.3	2.7

[a] *A, B, and C* represent the rotational constants (in MHz); *P_c* is the planar inertial moment (in $\text{u}\text{\AA}^2$), conversion factor: $505379.1 \text{ MHz}\cdot\text{u}\text{\AA}^2$; χ_{aa}, χ_{bb} and χ_{cc} are the diagonal elements of the ^{14}N nuclear quadrupole coupling tensor (in MHz), N_t and N_c correspond to the terminal and central ^{14}N nuclei, respectively; *N* is the Number of measured transitions and σ is the rms deviation of the fit (in kHz).

The first piece of evidence about the structure of the observed Gly-Gly rotamers come from the values of the planar inertial moment $P_c = (I_a + I_b - I_c)/2 = \sum m_i c_i^2$ (m_i, c_i are the mass and *c* coordinate of atom *i*), which gives the mass extension out of the *ab* inertial plane. Hence, the small *P_c* values of 5.18 and 5.16 $\text{u}\text{\AA}^2$ found for rotamers X and Y respectively (Table 1) indicate nearly planar heavy atom skeletons with the hydrogen atoms from methylene and amino groups as the sole out-of-plane mass contributors. In contrast, the larger *P_c* value of 34.98 $\text{u}\text{\AA}^2$ obtained for rotamer Z, points toward a conformer with a non planar skeleton. The procedure for definitely converting the spectroscopic Gly-Gly data into the corresponding conformational structures is based upon the quantitative match between the experimental values of the spectroscopic constants with those predicted theoretically. With this aim, an exhaustive conformational search was carried out using Amber force field.^[24] Then high-level MP2/6-311++G(d,p) *ab initio* calculations^[25] were employed to geometrically optimize all energetically accessible conformers below 1000 cm^{-1} . The predicted spectroscopic constants together with the electric dipole moment components for the predicted conformers are collected in Table 2. As shown in previous studies of amino acids,^[9,10,11] this level of theory predicts spectroscopic constants that are in close agreement with the experimental ones. Thus, a final comparison between the

experimental and theoretical values of rotational and quadrupole coupling constants in Tables 1 and 2 allows the identification of the rotamers X and Y as the planar conformers *pl* and *pll*, respectively, and the rotamer Z as the non-planar *npII* conformer of Gly-Gly.

Table 2. Spectroscopic Parameters and Relative Energies Calculated at the MP2/6-311++G(d,p) Level of Theory for Conformers of Gly-Gly.

	<i>pl</i>	<i>pll</i>	<i>npI</i>
<i>A/B/C</i> ^[a]	3075/858/685	3075/858/685	3115/960/879
<i>P_c</i> $\text{u}\text{\AA}^2$	7.5	5.7	56.7
$ \mu_a / \mu_b / \mu_c $	0.2/2.5/0.1	3.0/0.7/0.3	0.7/2.4/1.4
$^{14}\text{N}_t \chi_{aa}/\chi_{bb}/\chi_{cc}$	-3.20/2.75/0.44	-0.03/-1.62/1.65	0.17/2.81/-2.98
$^{14}\text{N}_c \chi_{aa}/\chi_{bb}/\chi_{cc}$	2.55/1.28/-3.83	2.37/2.07/-4.45	2.13/-0.46/-1.66
$\Delta E/\Delta G$	389/0	997/558	0/19
	<i>npII</i>	<i>npIII</i>	<i>npIV</i>
<i>A/B/C</i> ^[a]	3300/922/807	3186/964/890	3885/819/805
<i>P_c</i> $\text{u}\text{\AA}^2$	37.6	57.3	59.6
$ \mu_a / \mu_b / \mu_c $	6.6/2.1/1.3	3.2/3.6/0.6	2.9/0.2/1.3
$^{14}\text{N}_t \chi_{aa}/\chi_{bb}/\chi_{cc}$	-1.55/0.61/0.95	2.08/-0.36/-1.72	-1.24/1.02/0.22
$^{14}\text{N}_c \chi_{aa}/\chi_{bb}/\chi_{cc}$	1.78/1.18/-2.96	0.23/2.60/-2.83	1.91/-3.85/1.94
$\Delta E/\Delta G$	233/596	473/487	844/629

[a] *A, B, and C* represent the rotational constants (in MHz); *P_c* is the planar inertial moment (in $\text{u}\text{\AA}^2$), conversion factor: $505379.1 \text{ MHz}\cdot\text{u}\text{\AA}^2$; μ_a, μ_b and μ_c are the electric dipole moment components (in D); χ_{aa}, χ_{bb} and χ_{cc} are the diagonal elements of the ^{14}N nuclear quadrupole coupling tensor (in MHz), N_t and N_c correspond to the terminal and central ^{14}N nuclei, respectively; ΔE and ΔG are the relative and Gibbs energies (in cm^{-1}) at 298 K with respect to the global minimum calculated at the MP2/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory.

The structures of these three conformers (shown in Figure 2) are widely dominated by the flexibility of the NH_2 and COOH ends which allow the formation of strong intramolecular hydrogen bond interactions. Conformer *pl* is stabilized by two intramolecular hydrogen bonds, $\text{N}_c\text{-H}\cdots\text{O}=\text{C}$ and $\text{N}_c\text{-H}\cdots\text{N}_t$, with a *cis*-carboxylic arrangement. It results in an atypical two fused five-membered cyclic structure which is the main contribution to the overstabilization of its planar skeleton. The other planar form, *pll*, presents a bifurcated intramolecular interaction $\text{N}_t\text{-H}\cdots\text{O}=\text{C}$, while the N_cH group interacts with the carbonyl oxygen of the carboxylic moiety also in a *cis* disposition ($\text{N}_c\text{-H}\cdots\text{O}=\text{C}$ bond). The non-planar form, *npII*, is stabilized by the same $\text{N}_c\text{-H}\cdots\text{N}_t$ interaction found in the *pl* species but with a *trans*-carboxylic disposition, which allows to establish an intramolecular interaction, $\text{O-H}\cdots\text{O}=\text{C}$, closing a seven-membered ring.

Figure 2. The three observed conformers of Gly-Gly, showing the intramolecular interactions that stabilize the structures.

At this point, it must be noted that conformer *npI* is absent in the supersonic expansion despite it is predicted as the global minimum. This conflicting result questions the *ab initio* relative stabilities of the Gly-Gly conformers which seem to be in clear disagreement with the experimental results. Obviously one immediate question arises, is the *npI* conformer the global minimum of Gly-Gly dipeptide? A recent theoretical study pointed out problems using the MP2/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory in the reproduction the conformational energy landscape of non-rigid molecules.^[26] While the MP2 approach is useful for structure determination, the calculated energies are known to contain significant basis set superposition errors.^[27]

Figure 3. (Right) Electronic and (left) Gibbs free energies relative to *npI* conformer given by different DFT methods and MP2/6-311++G(d,p).

All above prompted us to extend our calculations on Gly-Gly dipeptide and further DFT calculations^[28] using different basis were employed to estimate the relative energies for these six conformers. As shown in Figure 3, DFT calculations predict *pI* and *npI* conformers as isoenergetic, in right contrast with MP2 predictions, being the *pI* conformer the global minimum in most of the calculations. In this new scenario, the absence of *npI* conformer can be associated to a collisional relaxation to conformer *pI* through a low-energy interconversion barrier. Certain conformers that are thermally populated at the pre-expansion conditions may collisionally relax to lower energy conformers and hence be "missing" following the jet expansion as have been already shown for several α -amino acids.^[29-32] Ruoff *et al.*^[33] have deduced that collisional removal of a higher energy conformer is possible when the isomerization barrier is lower than 400 cm^{-1} .

Figure 4. Potential energy profiles between conformers *npI* and *pI* calculated at the M06-2x/aug-cc-pVTZ level of theory.

Figure 4 illustrates the energy profile calculated for the interconversion between the *npI* and *pI* conformers, changing the CN_cCC dihedral angle, and barriers heights ranging from 24 to 36 cm^{-1} , computed using different basis set, were found. This explains the non-observation of conformer *npI* in the supersonic expansion. The same reasoning can be used to justify the absence of conformers *npIII* and *npIV*. The relaxation pathway of conformer *npIV* into the *pII* was calculated (Fig.S1 of the Supporting Information) through the variation of the CN_cCC angle, providing an interconversion barrier of 45 cm^{-1} that rationalizes the non detection of *npIV* species. A two step relaxation process could explain the absence of conformer *npIII* in the supersonic expansion. Conformer *npIII* can first relax to *npI* by changing the $\text{N}_c\text{CC}=\text{O}$ angle (Fig. S1 of the Supporting Information) overpassing a barrier around 240 cm^{-1} , which subsequently relaxes to *pI* conformer according to the profile shown in Figure 4. Additionally, the interconversion profiles between the observed species have been calculated and barrier heights around 1300 - 1500 cm^{-1} were found. The observed and "missing" conformers of Gly-Gly dipeptide and the conformational isomerization pathways are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Lowest energy conformers of Gly-Gly. The structures are labeled by the planarity or not of the heavy atom skeletons (p or np) and with an additional index going up with increasing energy. The three observed conformers are

encircled. The arrows indicate the conformational interconversion pathways (see text).

In summary, the benefits derived from vaporization by laser ablation and the high resolution and sensitivity attained by LA-MB-FTMW spectroscopy have provided the first experimental information on the structure of the simplest dipeptide Gly-Gly. The spectroscopic constants derived from the separated spectra of three observed species compared with those predicted theoretically provide an unmatched means to achieve an unambiguous identification of the observed conformers and constitute a unique benchmark to test the different computational methods. As a consequence of collisional relaxation at the onset of the supersonic expansion, the number of observed conformers does not comprise all thermally accessible forms corresponding to the equilibrium distribution predicted by theoretical calculations. Despite this, the three forms characterized here along with the postulated "missing" conformers provides the first global picture of the conformational behavior of the neutral form for simplest dipeptide Gly-Gly, which has been remained unknown up to now. Conformer interconversion enhances the notion that the conformational behavior of Gly-Gly dipeptide is, to some extent, dynamic.

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- [1] T. Häber, K. Seefeld, G. Engler, S. Grimme, K. Kleinermanns. *Chem. Phys. Chem.* **2008**, *10*, 2844-2851.
- [2] T. Häber, K. Seefeld, K. Kleinermanns. *J. Phys. Chem. A* **2007**, *111*, 3038-3046.
- [3] I. Hünig, K. A. Seefeld, K. Kleinermanns. *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **2003**, *369*, 173-179.
- [4] I. Hünig, K. Kleinermanns. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2004**, *6*, 2650-2658.
- [5] D. Řeha, H. Valdés, J. Vondrášek, P. Hobza, A. Abu-Riziq, B. Crews, M. S. de Vries, *Chem-Eur J.* **2005**, *11*, 6803-6817.
- [6] A. Abo-Riziq, L. Grace, B. Crews, M. P. Callahan, T. Van Mourik, M. S. de Vries, *J. Phys. Chem. A*, **2011**, *115*, 6077-6087.
- [7] J. M. Bakker, C. Plützer, I. Hünig, T. Häber, I. Compagnon, G. von Helden, G. Meijer, K. Kleinermanns. *Chem. Phys. Chem.* **2005**, *6*, 120-128.
- [8] a) L. R. Wright, R. F. Borkman. *J. Phys. Chem.* **1982**, *86*, 3956-3962. b) A. Gil, J. Bertrán, M. Sodupe. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2006**, *124*, 154306. c) W. Yu, X. Xu, H. Li, R. Pang, K. Fang, Z. Lin. *J. Comput. Chem.* **2009**, *30*, 2105-2121. d) V. Feyer, O. Plekan, R. Richter, M. Coreno, K. C. Prince, V. Carraveta. *J. Phys. Chem. A* **2009**, *113*, 10726-10733.
- [9] J. L. Alonso and J. C. López, *Microwave Spectroscopy of Biomolecular Building Blocks in Topics in Current Chemistry*, **2015**, vol. 364, pp. 335-402.
- [10] I. Peña, M. E. Sanz, J. C. López and J. L. Alonso, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2012**, *134*, 2305-2312.
- [11] C. Cabezas, M. Varela, I. Peña, S. Mata, J. C. López and J. L. Alonso, *Chem. Commun.* **2012**, *48*, 5934-5936.
- [12] C. Cabezas, M. Varela, V. Cortijo, A. I. Jiménez, I. Peña, A. M. Daly, J. C. López, C. Cativiela, J. L. Alonso, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2013**, *15*, 2580-2585.
- [13] C. Cabezas, M. Varela, J. L. Alonso, *Chem. Phys. Chem.* **2013**, *14*, 2539-2543.
- [14] C. Puzzarini, M. Biczysko, V. Barone, L. Largo, I. Peña, C. Cabezas and J. L. Alonso, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2014**, *5*, 534-540.
- [15] C. Cabezas, M. A. T. Robben, A. M. Rijs, I. Peña and J. L. Alonso, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2015**, *17*, 20274-20280.
- [16] M. E. Sanz, C. Cabezas, S. Mata, J. L. Alonso, *J. Chem. Phys.* **2014**, *140*, 204308.
- [17] I. Peña, C. Cabezas and J. L. Alonso *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2015**, *54*, 2991-2994.
- [18] C. Pérez, S. Mata, C. Cabezas, J. C. López and J. L. Alonso, *J. Phys. Chem. A* **2015**, *119*, 3731-3735.
- [19] W. Gordy, R. L. Cook, *Microwave Molecular Spectra*, 3rd ed., Wiley, New York, **1984**.
- [20] C. Bermúdez, S. Mata, C. Cabezas, and J. L. Alonso, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2014**, *53*, 11015-11018.
- [21] H. M. Pickett, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.*, **1991**, *148*, 371
- [22] J. K. G. Watson, in *Vibrational Spectra and Structure*, Vol. 6 (Ed.: J. R. Durig), Elsevier, New York, **1977**, pp. 1-78.
- [23] H. M. Foley, *Phys. Rev.* **1947**, *71*, 747.
- [24] D. A. Case *et al.*, AMBER 2015, University of California, San Francisco, **2015**.
- [25] Gaussian 09, Revision A.1, M. J. Frisch *et al.*, Gaussian Inc., Wallingford CT, **2009**.
- [26] L. Goerigk, A. Karton, J. M. L. Martin, L. Radom, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2013**, *15*, 7028-7031.
- [27] S. Grimme, *J. Comput. Chem.* **2004**, *25*, 1463-1473.
- [28] a) Y. Zhao, D. G. Truhlar, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2007**, *3*, 289-300. b) S. Grimme, *J. Chem. Phys.* **2006**, *124*, 034108.
- [29] P. D. Godfrey, R. D. Brown, F. M. Rodgers *J. Mol. Struct.* **1996**, *376*, 65-81.
- [30] S. Blanco, A. Lesarri, J. C. López and J. L. Alonso, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2004**, *126*, 11675-11683.
- [31] E. J. Cocinero, A. Lesarri, Jens-Uwe Grabow, J. C. López and J. L. Alonso, *Chem. Phys. Chem.* **2007**, *8*, 599-604.
- [32] A. Lesarri, E. J. Cocinero, J. C. López and J. L. Alonso, *Angew. Chem.* **2004**, *116*, 615-620.
- [33] R. S. Ruoff, T. D. Klots, T. Emilsson, H. S. Gutowsky, *J. Chem. Phys.* **1990**, *93*, 3142-3150.
- [34] G. T. Fraser, R. D. Suenram, and C. L. Lugez, *J. Phys. Chem. A* **2000**, *104*, 1141-1146.

COMMUNICATION

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